

SHORT NOTES

DOUBLE SALTS OF OXYFLUOBORATES WITH SULPHATES AND FLUOBERYLLATES

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Double salts are generally formed between alkali metals and those of bivalent or trivalent metals. The important double salts formed by the sulphates are the schonites and alums.

The pure alkali metal or ammonium oxyfluoborates have not yet been isolated. The addition of calculated amounts of alkali fluoride or ammonium fluoride and hydrofluoric acid to boric acid results in the formation of fluoborates and hydroxyfluoborates. The double salts of ammonium sulphate or fluoberyllate with the oxyfluoborates of the bivalent metals have been prepared.

As these anions, e.g., SO_4^{2-} , BeF_4^{2-} and BF_3O^{2-} , are isomorphous, it is very difficult to obtain the double salts with 1:1 proportion. Isomorphous replacement invariably takes place and the ratios of SO_4^{2-} or BeF_4^{2-} to BF_3O^{2-} in the final compounds depend upon their respective solubilities. In this paper the analysis of only those crops are given where the ratios of the anions are approximately 1:1.

Procedure.—Concentrated solutions of equimolecular proportions of ammonium sulphate or fluoberyllate and oxyfluoborates were mixed and allowed to evaporate at room temperature in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 (conc.). The first crop which appeared after one or two days was rejected as it was liable to contain a greater proportion of sulphates or fluoberyllates, as the case might be. The next crop was isolated. It was filtered under suction, washed once with water and then with 60% alcohol and dried in air. In subsequent crops, the proportions of the sulphate or fluoberyllate to the oxyfluoborate remained almost constant. In all these compounds the percentages of SO_4^{2-} were higher than those required for 1:1 replacement. This is obviously due to the lower solubilities of the pure sulphate double salts. But in the case of fluoberyllate, almost theoretical percentages were obtained due to the higher solubility of these double salts than those containing sulphate.

Ammonium sulphate - copper oxyfluoborate hexahydrate was obtained from ammonium sulphate and copper oxyfluoborate pentahydrate. It is a pale blue crystalline substance, indistinguishable from the double sulphate. [Found: SO_4 , 25.85; B, 2.68. $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CuBOF}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires SO_4 , 24.77; B, 2.79%].

Ammonium sulphate - nickel oxyfluoborate hexahydrate is a pale green crystalline substance, obtained from ammonium sulphate and nickel oxyfluoborate hexahydrate. [Found: SO_4 , 26.00; B, 2.70. $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{NiBOF}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires SO_4 , 25.19; B, 2.83%].

Ammonium sulphate - cobalt oxyfluoborate hexahydrate was obtained from ammonium sulphate and cobalt oxyfluoborate heptahydrate. It is a soluble and pink-coloured substance. [Found: SO_4 , 25.77; B, 2.69. $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CoBOF}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires SO_4 , 25.09; B, 2.82%].

Ammonium sulphate - zinc oxyfluoborate hexahydrate. [Found: SO_4 , 25.21; B, 2.60. $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{ZnBOF}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires SO_4 , 24.68; B, 2.78%].

Ammonium sulphate - cadmium oxyfluoborate hexahydrate was obtained as a white crystalline substance by mixing concentrated solutions of the constituents. It was washed with 60% alcohol in which $\text{CdBOF}_3 \cdot 8/3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was soluble but not the double salt. [Found: SO_4 , 22.48; B, 2.40. $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CdBOF}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires SO_4 , 22.02; B, 2.48%].

Ammonium fluoberyllate - copper oxyfluoborate hexahydrate was obtained, as described above, as a pale blue crystalline substance. [Found: F, 34.80; Be, 2.44. $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{CuBOF}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires F, 35.34; Be, 2.39%].

Ammonium fluoberyllate - cadmium oxyfluoborate hexahydrate was obtained in the same way as described above. It is a colorless, crystalline, non-hygroscopic substance. [Found: Be, 2.20; B, 2.34. $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{CdBOF}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Be, 2.11; B, 2.54%].

Ammonium fluoberyllate - zinc oxyfluoborate hexahydrate. [Found: F, 34.73; Be, 2.34. $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{ZnBOF}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires F, 35.18; Be, 2.38%].

Ammonium fluoberyllate - nickel oxyfluoborate hexahydrate was obtained in the same way as the copper compound, as a pale green crystalline substance. [Found: F, 38.0; Be, 2.40. $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{NiBOF}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires F, 38.49; Be, 2.42%].

Ammonium fluoberyllate - cobalt oxyfluoborate hexahydrate is a pink-coloured crystalline substance, fairly soluble in water. [Found: Be, 2.54; B, 2.76. $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{CoBOF}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Be, 2.42; B, 2.90%].

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